

Project Proposal: Iot Based Smart Gardening and Irrigation System

A Project Proposal

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of Science (Honors) in Computer Science and Engineering

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Motivation:

The robot is used for plants' watering systems. In today's busy life, people forget to water plants or go on vacation. But the plants need to be watered. In this case, our robot will sense the moisture of the soil, environmental temperature, and humidity [1]. The owner can see the level of soil moisture on his/her phone and control the watering through his/her mobile phone. We present the design and development of fully autonomous, cost effective and efficient system for watering indoor plants that are placed on a surface at even distance. The system comprised of a smart mini robot which is comprised of an Arduino microcontroller, motors, motor drive, water tank, water pump, a wireless communication radio [2]. Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) module has the main functions such as navigation; carry water for watering the plants and uses wireless communication to communicate with the plant subsystem. The other main part of the system is potted plants, which is comprised of Arduino microcontroller, soil moisture sensor and wireless communication module which are responsible for functions such as sense the amount of moisture present in the soil and send signals to the smart mini robot when in need of water. As per the amount of soil moisture present in the soil, which is sensed by sensing module, the watering needs of the plants will be fulfilled by the smart mini robot. This smart mini robot is fully capable of receiving the signal from the potted plants, navigate towards plants, locating the plants and pumping the water to the plants without any human intervention. To autonomously maneuver near the mobile robot, a predefined path is used and for identifying each plant in the system, an RFID tag is attached to each plant. Apart from the architecture this paper also describes the comprehensive implementation of the system [3]. This paper concludes with the system performance evaluation and future project extensions where this system can be reviewed and enhanced.

Specific Objectives:

Smart robot; Watering system; Radio Frequency Identification; Soil moisture sensor; Plant watering; Xbee 3; Internet of Thing (IoT); Autonomous system.

Specific Outcome: To control the moisture content of the soil of rooftop garden or indoor plants [4]. According to soil moisture, water pumping motor turned on or off through the mobile. To saves water, while the water level can be obtained in a preferred aspect of the plant, thereby increasing the growing level of plants. To reduce waste of water and save time in our busy life and also the system is smart [5].

To allow the delivery to the plant when needed based on the type of plant, soil moisture, and observed temperature. To create a cost effective technology. To reduce the hard work.

Methodology:

DC Motor using water pump

DC motor to make water pump. DC motor has two leads one is positive and another one is negative. If we connect them directly to the Arduino board then it will damage the board. To overcome this problem, NPN transistor is used to control the switching activity of the motor according to the code. Soil moisture sensor,

The soil moisture sensor consists of two leads that are used to measure volume of water content in soil [6]. These leads allow the current to pass through the soil and in return calculates the resistance value to measure the moisture level. If there is more water in soil then soil will conduct more electricity, means less resistance value along with high level of moisture. In the same manner if there is less water in soil then soil will conduct less electricity, means high resistance value along with low level of moisture [7].

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